

The research infrastructures from the perspective of systems ecology

- a knowledge mapping -

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1 Introduction

The strategic goal of systems ecology is to unveil the full complexity of socio-ecological systems, from simple to large-scale processes, and to provide an organized image of the diversity of approaches and their epistemic complementarity. Research infrastructures have emerged over the last twenty years (figure 1) as tools for addressing complex research and/or monitoring programs.

Figure 1: Dynamics of publications with “research infrastructure” OR “research infrastructures” in their topic (citation report from Web of Science, July 2025).

The objective of this report is to map the scientific knowledge about research infrastructures relevant for the goal of systems ecology and interpret the findings.

2 Method

Searching in Web of Science for ("Research infrastructure" OR "research infrastructures") AND ("research program" OR "monitoring program") returned only 54 publications organized by categories as in Figure 2. One can notice that only four articles are in the category of Environmental Sciences, and none in other potentially relevant categories, indicating the absence of a direct description of the relationship between research infrastructures and the research and monitoring programs relevant for systems ecology.

In this context, I investigated the separate bodies of literature about research infrastructures and research or monitoring programs (Table 2) in seven WoS categories: environmental sciences, ecology, marine freshwater biology, biodiversity conservation, environmental studies, forestry, and water resources.

The total number of articles with "research infrastructure" OR "research infrastructures" in topic (title, abstract, and key word) selected by the seven categories was small enough to focus the analysis on it (335 articles – core set - cited by 6250 articles - extended). The core and the extended set were analyzed with CiteSpace. The core set of 335 articles was also inspected article by article, and a subset of about 120 articles was selected using expert knowledge to cover the diversity of approaches in this body of literature.

Figure 2 Distribution of articles about research infrastructures and monitoring/research programs by WoS category.

Table 1 Number of articles in WoS with keywords about research infrastructures and research or monitoring programs in the topic (top), in the title (down), and percentages from the total in the topic in selected categories (middle).

Key words	WoS in topic, number of articles							
	All	Environmental Sciences	Ecology	Marine Feshwater biology	Biodiversity conservation	Environmental studies	Forestry	Water resources
"research infrastructure" OR "research infrastructures"	3801	225	50	32	34	59	13	8
"research program"	22894	1074	346	167	94	217	164	329
"monitoring program"	10757	2534	826	727	398	122	120	770

Key words	WoS in topic, percents from total							
		Environmental Sciences	Ecology	Marine Feshwater biology	Biodiversity conservation	Environmental studies	Forestry	Water resources
"research infrastructure" OR "research infrastructures"		5.92	1.32	0.84	0.89	1.55	0.34	0.21
"research program"		4.69	1.51	0.73	0.41	0.95	0.72	1.44
"monitoring program"		23.56	7.68	6.76	3.70	1.13	1.12	7.16

Key words	WoS in title, number of articles							
	All	Environmental Sciences	Ecology	Marine Feshwater biology	Biodiversity conservation	Environmental studies	Forestry	Water resources
"research infrastructure" OR "research infrastructures"	488	16	6	3	4	8	0	0
"research program"	3956	178	45	13	7	34	38	56
"monitoring program"	1813	267	72	63	28	12	13	86

The number of articles with keywords about research programs and monitoring programs in the topic was much larger, so I focused the analysis on the articles with these keywords in their title and then selected by the seven WoS categories (280 about research programs, and 406 about monitoring programs). They were analysed together with their extended set of 7568 articles by CiteSpace.

3 Results

3.1 CiteSpace analysis

Figure 3 shows the timeline of the clusters of literature dealing with research infrastructures in the selected WoS categories, and Figure 4 shows the timeline of the clusters mentioning research and monitoring programs. The keywords of the clusters are presented in Appendix 1 (for infrastructures) and Appendix 3 (for programs). Appendices 2 and 4 show the main publications from selected clusters, allowing the reader to go to each publication by hyperlink. I will not develop here a detailed interpretation of the patterns observed in the clusters. They are provided here as input for anyone interested in a more in-depth analysis.

Figure 3. Cluster timeline for the literature on research infrastructures, with a citation network for 2022. Each node is a strongly cited article, and its size corresponds to its centrality in the network. The name of the cluster is a frequent keyword.

Figure 4. Similar to Figure 3, which presents the literature on research/monitoring programs, this figure also includes a citation network for 2023.

Two other interesting aspects are:

- The decoupling of the literature about monitoring programs and research programs (Figure 5). We analysed them together, but actually, the production pics are located in different years for the two topics. The number of articles for the search "research program" AND "monitoring program" in the topic is 42, and in the title is one, which is about three orders of magnitude less than when searched separately.
- The correlation between the number of authors from different countries citing the articles about the research infrastructures and research/monitoring programs (figure 6). This suggests that the scientific production is controlled by country-level properties irrespective of the decoupling between scientific subjects.

Figure 5 Publications and citations about monitoring programs (left) and research programs (right) between 1975 and 2025 in Web of Science in the seven domains.

Figure 5 Correlation between the citations of articles in the analysed areas by authors in different countries (scientific infrastructure and research programs)

3.2 An organized bibliography relevant for research infrastructures

An organized bibliography for the topic of research infrastructures is presented in Appendix 5 and includes the following categories:

1. Literature about the history of research infrastructures
2. Social, economic, and political constraints on the development of research infrastructures
3. Scientific constraints on the development of research infrastructure
 - a. The nature of scientific knowledge, the case of ecology and environmental sciences
 - b. Research techniques in ecology
 - c. The experimental design in ecology and environmental sciences

- d. Knowledge frontiers in ecology and environmental sciences
- 4. The structure and functioning of research infrastructures
 - a. The diversity of approaches
 - b. The problem of interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity
 - c. LTER Case Study
 - d. GEOBON Case Study
 - e. ERIC Case Study

Besides the bibliography, I provide two tables showing the fine structure of the publications in categories 2 and 4a (tables 2 and 3).

Table 2 The distribution of articles by subject in the category „Social, economic and political constraints on the development of research infrastructures”.

Subject	Publication
<i>Policy, economics, sociology</i>	
RI for cultural and political integration in the EU	(Cramer and Rüffin 2024)
Policy instruments for the knowledge economy	(Cooke 2004)
Research policy, institutionalization of scientific collaboration	(Jacob and Hallonsten 2012, Franssen 2020, Fecher et al. 2021, Aarden 2023)
Coevolution of RI and scientific progress	(Yu et al. 2021)
Identity criteria and organisational diversity of RI	(Xu et al. 2017, Hallonsten 2020, Eggleton 2024)
Science diplomacy to build international RI	(Lima-Toivanen et al. 2025)
Return on investment in RI	(Mayernik et al. 2016, Chabbi et al. 2017, Rådberg and Löfsten 2023, Yström et al. 2025)
<i>Coordination and management of RI</i>	
Diversification of RI objectives	(Bonet-García et al. 2023)
Financial efficiency, sustainability of RI	(Zakaria et al. 2021, Novikova 2022, Saleh Contell et al. 2022)
Global scale integration of RI	(Petzold et al. 2024)
<i>Public-private cooperation</i>	
Cooperation of RI with the private sector	(Chabbi et al. 2017, Rådberg and Löfsten 2023, Yström et al. 2025)
Innovation ecosystems	(Li-Ying et al. 2022)
RI for large-scale natural capital management	(Martínez-López et al. 2019)

Table 3. The types of infrastructures revealed by the literature selected in the category about the diversity of approaches.

Type or RI	Publication
<i>Monitoring</i>	
Wildlife research and monitoring	(Black et al. 2025)
Pollination services monitoring	(Breeze et al. 2020)
Farm monitoring	(Collins et al. 2025)
Forest monitoring	(Sekot 2017, Zweifel et al. 2023)
Terrestrial monitoring (observatories)	(Hamilton et al. 2007, Zacharias et al. 2024)
Atmospheric monitoring	(Heikkinen et al. 2020, Lappalainen et al. 2021, Lapenna et al. 2025)
<i>Research</i>	
Ecophysiology and population ecology of trees	(Jansma et al. 2012, Grossman et al. 2018)
Mobile mesocosms	(Fink et al. 2020, Roy et al. 2021)
Long-term large-scale experiments	(Ellison et al. 2010)
Critical zone observatories	(Gaillardet et al. 2018, Naylor et al. 2023)
Hydrological research	(Nasta et al. 2025)
Marine/large river basin research	(Irvine et al. 2016, Farcy et al. 2019, Klein et al. 2019, Steinhoff et al. 2019, Lo Bue et al. 2021, Dañoibeitia et al. 2023)
Clean production, industrial ecology	(Peck and Parker 2016)
Global research networks	(Nativi et al. 2014, López-Ballesteros et al. 2018, Vicca et al. 2018, Nieto-Lugilde et al. 2021, Loescher et al. 2022)
<i>Data</i>	
Big data infrastructure	(Pettit et al. 2017, Jaric et al. 2020)
<i>Modeling</i>	
Virtual laboratory	(Lenzen et al. 2014)
<i>Knowledge transfer, transformative processes</i>	
Living lab (research – industry – stakeholders)	(Von Geibler et al. 2014, Liedtke et al. 2015, Abi Saad and Agogué 2024, John 2024)
Real-world laboratories	(Schneidewind et al. 2018, Kampfmann et al. 2023, Kampfmann et al. 2024, Temperton et al. 2025)

4 Discussions

4.1 Fitting the findings in the diversity of socio-ecological approaches

Table 4 presents a simplified view of strategies for dimensionality reduction of socio-ecological processes, enabling their conceptualization at varying levels of complexity. Corroborating its content with the content of table 2, 3 and the Appendixes 1-4 one can notice that the research infrastructures can be treated from social sciences point of view from organisational studies, to populations and communities of organizations, can be approached by social coevolutionary processes, can be included in innovation ecosystems and other large scale entities relevant for industrial ecology and are directly relevant by policies and by their consequences on development for the full-scale socio-economic systems. At the same time, they are tools for implementing monitoring and research programs in strategies from the ecophysiological and population level (e.g., in the case of trees) to ecosystem ecology and transformative socio-ecological approaches.

Table 4. A simplified classification of the epistemic strategies reducing the complexity of productive processes in the complementary natural and social domains. The gradient of blue color suggests a continuum from individualistic (Gleasonian) positions to holistic (Clementsian) ones. The strategies E1, E2, and E3 traditionally belong to the domain of biology, while the E4 and ES5 strategies belong to Earth system science (from [Iordache 2024](#)).

Field	Ecological objects and processes					
Epistemic strategy	E1 Eco-physiological	E2 Population ecology	E3a Community ecology	E3b Systems of coevolved populations (biocenoses)	E4 Ecosystem ecology	ES5 Systems ecology Theories about adaptive cycles
	S1 Management theory, organisational studies	S2 Ecology of populations of organizations	S3a Ecology of communities of organizations. Action arenas	S3b Theories about the evolution of culture/institutions	S4 Industrial ecology, other physicalist approaches	Theories about general social and economic structures
Field	Social, economic and cultural objects and processes					

4.2 Comparison with AI output

Searching in Google for the topic of a lecture about research infrastructures returned the following points:

Key aspects of research infrastructures

- Facilities and Resources
- Services
- Diverse Fields
- European Landscape
- Funding and Sustainability
- Strategic Importance

Examples

- Large-scale facilities
- Distributed facilities
- Data repositories and databases

The role of research infrastructures

- Advancing Scientific Knowledge
- Driving Innovation
- Addressing Societal Challenges
- Regional Development

One can notice that the analytic effort of personal searching in Web of Science, mapping with CiteSpace, selecting the literature based on expert knowledge and complementing it with other

indirectly relevant literature, especially about the nature of scientific knowledge and the techniques needed to make use of research infrastructures effectively, offered a more meaningful image of the topic compared to the A. We included aspects like the history of the approach, the epistemic strategies, the international image of the topic, relationships with research and monitoring programs, all of which allow a useful understanding of the nature of the subject of research infrastructure, not encouraging to treat them as a goal in itself. The difference between human and AI output results from the fact that AI uses only mainstream publications explicitly referring to research infrastructure, which may be appropriate when the research field is mature, but less so when the topic is emergent and highly dynamic from a scientific and applied point of view.

Organizing a lecture about research infrastructures in detail will depend on the organizational provider, the audience's interests, and the audience's profile. I have provided here a few resources for those interested in this topic, which can be used creatively to tailor to the needs.

5 Conclusions

I have searched for literature on research infrastructure, research programs, and monitoring programs, identified clusters of publications and trends over time and by country using CiteSpace, selected representative articles on research infrastructure, and organized a structured bibliography on this topic.

The problem of research infrastructures is embedded in the problem of research and monitoring programs, which can now be fully understood in the context of socio-ecological development, particularly within the framework of the knowledge society. The history of the explicit notion of research infrastructure is rather short, and the scientific literature about this topic is growing rapidly. There is already a body of social sciences literature studying these kinds of entities from various perspectives, and knowing this literature is crucial to understanding what is at stake by research infrastructures from economic and political perspectives. At the same time, if one limits oneself to this literature, it creates a false image about the value of these infrastructures in themselves. Investing in them can yield the desired returns only when combined with sound science and monitoring, from conceptualization to implementation, and with a strong understanding that science evolves and that all approaches are valuable for solving specific problems. Research infrastructures in environmental sciences and related ones might be more valuable when they allow very diverse services, not setting the research, monitoring, and management agenda of the end users, but encouraging as diverse and creative a use as possible. A combination of the diversity of research infrastructures and the diversity of purposes when using them sets the population of programs and projects from which the people and society will benefit the most. Besides this reactive use, based on the currently perceived advantages in the society, strategic uses by large national and international actors are to be encouraged as well, for proactive reasons and adaptive ones to the potential long-term changes.

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Appendix 1. Clusters summary for the literature about research infrastructure.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	141	0.968	2020	human health; food service sector; quality evaluation; covid pollution; global plastic waste footprint co-infecting microbe; dual hesitant q-rung orthopair; covid-19 era; environmental externalities; covid-19 scenario	covid-19 pandemic (6197.89, 1.0E-4); waste management (2106.02, 1.0E-4); personal protective equipment (1169.03, 1.0E-4); plastic pollution (712.04, 1.0E-4); microfiber pollution (686.28, 1.0E-4)	protective personal equipment (1.42); identifying
2	101	0.98	2017	particle extinction coefficient profile; early detection; stratospheric fire smoke layer; new instrument; iberian peninsula enhancing mobile aerosol monitoring; situ surface measurement; central european research station melpitz; stratospheric wildfire smoke; mineral dust concentration	situ measurement (1043.2, 1.0E-4); lidar observation (969.08, 1.0E-4); ice-nucleating particle (881.1, 1.0E-4); polarization lidar (719.2, 1.0E-4); wildfire smoke (686.84, 1.0E-4)	air mass trajectories (0.84); ceilometer photomete
3	100	0.882	2016	insecticide use; fungal diversity; chilean long-term socio-ecological research network; stream macroinvertebrate community metrics; landscape concept tree species; south africa; oil palm landscape; forest ecosystem functioning; adriatic sea	tree diversity (1162.21, 1.0E-4); tree diversity effect (1054.01, 1.0E-4); covid-19 pandemic (727.72, 1.0E-4); international long term (635.53, 1.0E-4); ecological research network (635.53, 1.0E-4)	big data access (1.69); ecosystem function (1.69);
4	93	0.944	2017	key approaches; eddy covariance dataset; covid-19 economic downturn; european arctic; weighted data synthesis knowledge base; key approaches; south africa; essential earth observation variable; cloud technologies	covid-19 pandemic (1026.67, 1.0E-4); essential variable (629.63, 1.0E-4); tropospheric ozone (525.05, 1.0E-4); mediterranean sea (520.31, 1.0E-4); european ocean (440.58, 1.0E-4)	big data access (2.37); ecosystem function (2.37);
5	93	0.978	2021	risk assessment; monitoring stem growth phenology; conserving evolutionary potential; monitoring method; forest-atmosphere exchange risk assessment; monitoring stem growth phenology; woodland restoration; conserving evolutionary potential; mobilization effort	covid-19 pandemic (729.89, 1.0E-4); digital twin (725.38, 1.0E-4); blue economy (604.23, 1.0E-4); central europe (520.16, 1.0E-4); tasmanian midland (439.49, 1.0E-4)	big data access (1.7); ecosystem function (1.7); p
6	69	0.959	2013	ecosystem service; disaster-related data; using spatiotemporal pattern; soil moisture mapping; land cover change approach live monitoring; model integration process; javascript invocation rule; business processes; brokering service	global monitoring (226.37, 1.0E-4); biological invasion (226.37, 1.0E-4); innovation opportunities (215.56, 1.0E-4); future internet technologies (204.74, 1.0E-4); environmental application (204.74, 1.0E-4)	big data access (0.02); indexing service modeling
8	40	0.984	2010	foundation species loss; global capacity; lifewatch approach; flowering plant; open future harvard forest hemlock removal; global capacity; woolly adelgid; nitrogen losses; information system	open future (324.86, 1.0E-4); biodiversity knowledge discovery (142.03, 1.0E-4); biological collections ontology (142.03, 1.0E-4); woolly adelgid (129.05, 1.0E-4); nitrogen losses (129.05, 1.0E-4)	covid-19 pandemic (0.01); ecosystem function (0.01)
9	34	0.998	2013	heilongjiang province; low-carbon socioeconomic transition; northeast china; tropical cyclone; economic damage flexible algorithm; hybrid life-cycle assessment; sectoral disaggregation; new level; self-healing road	multi-regional input-output table (213.34, 1.0E-4); consumption-based accounting (189.53, 1.0E-4); input-output model (189.53, 1.0E-4); linking city-level input-output table (177.64, 1.0E-4); construction framework (177.64, 1.0E-4)	low-carbon socioeconomic transition (0.01); northe
10	34	0.999	2017	urban sustainability; greenhouse gas emissions-a; systematic review; community intervention; photovoltaic tis livable urban space; real-world lab wuppertal; new dawn; circular forest bioeconomy; real-world context	real-world lab (660.85, 1.0E-4); german cities (479.26, 1.0E-4); technological innovation system (408.34, 1.0E-4); real-world laboratories (353.24, 1.0E-4); demonstration project (345.36, 1.0E-4)	community intervention (0.13); greenhouse gas emis
11	32	0.999	2021	temporal dynamics; using positive matrix factorization; european air quality modelling; aerosol mass spectrometry; ambient air north china plain; source contribution analysis; aerosol chemical composition; meteorological condition; different season	source apportionment (624.14, 1.0E-4); organic aerosol source (436.73, 1.0E-4); carbonaceous aerosol (305.93, 1.0E-4); using aethalometer data (269.65, 1.0E-4); ebc source apportionment (269.65, 1.0E-4)	european air quality modelling (0.13); enhancing a

13	29	0.966	2018	future research direction; research infrastructure; joint effort; fluorescent polypropylene nanoplastics; zebrafish embryo raising social awareness; academic interest; potential route; food container; intermittent sardinian river	plastic waste (349.97, 1.0E-4); potential carcinogenic factor (250.11, 1.0E-4); mitigation pathway (240.55, 1.0E-4); change-breaking carbon lock-in (240.55, 1.0E-4); rural communities (231.01, 1.0E-4)	big data access (0.04); ecosystem function (0.04);
15	28	0.981	2020	sustainable energy transition; transitional housing; residential building stock; effective reuse; wooden single-family building-focusing stakeholder promotion strategies; effective reuse; new framework; dual force; stakeholder perspective	circular construction (725.29, 1.0E-4); information gap (275.2, 1.0E-4); building material reuse (275.2, 1.0E-4); building-city synergy (266.57, 1.0E-4); circular transformation (266.57, 1.0E-4)	construction project (0.09); stakeholder perspecti
16	25	0.995	2020	ethical ecology; halogen-ozone cycle; ground-based measurement; fire activity; summer storm	zeppelin observatory svalbard (409.62, 1.0E-4); long-term comprehensive observation (297.17, 1.0E-4); different environment (297.17, 1.0E-4); multiple grand challenge (297.17, 1.0E-4); biological processes (289.43, 1.0E-4)	big data access (0.14); ecosystem function (0.14);
17	23	1	2007	environmental science; tropical biology; international collaboration; combining interdisciplinary; crossing boundaries local stakeholder; knowledge exchange; resource conservation initiative; sharing ecological knowledge; graduate student	sharing ecological knowledge (108.69, 1.0E-4); resource conservation initiative (93.02, 1.0E-4); developing social learning partnership (93.02, 1.0E-4); southern africa (93.02, 1.0E-4); local stakeholder (77.42, 1.0E-4)	covid-19 pandemic (0.01); waste management (0); fu
18	17	0.998	2021	northern hemisphere midlatitude tropopause inversion; oyster shell; indirect carbonation; probiotic encapsulation; hydrogen aircraft weather-induced uncertainties; radiosonde observation; persistent contrail; ice supersaturation; upper air water vapour profile	contrail cirrus (353.25, 1.0E-4); persistent contrail formation (276.62, 1.0E-4); environmental factor (276.62, 1.0E-4); reanalysis weather data (267.06, 1.0E-4); ground-based contrail observation (267.06, 1.0E-4)	northern hemisphere midlatitude tropopause inversi
20	13	1	2018	forestry intensification; landscape ecology; international forest biodiversity target; regional social-ecological system; green infrastructure social capital; landscape governance; vibrant forest landscape; decision-making processes; comparative review	integrated landscape approaches (278.59, 1.0E-4); assessing habitat network functionality (269.85, 1.0E-4); forest exploitation (269.85, 1.0E-4); case study region (269.85, 1.0E-4); forestry intensification (261.13, 1.0E-4)	touristic challenge (0.08); integrated planning (0
24	10	0.995	2015	big data analytics; spatial cumulative sum algorithm; processing; in-mapper combiner; mapreduce algorithm processing; in-mapper combiner; mapreduce algorithm; big data analytics; spatial cumulative sum algorithm	in-mapper combiner (38.71, 1.0E-4); processing (38.71, 1.0E-4); mapreduce algorithm (38.71, 1.0E-4); spatial cumulative sum algorithm (19.21, 1.0E-4); big data analytics (19.21, 1.0E-4)	covid-19 pandemic (0.02); waste management (0); fu
25	9	0.984	2013	processes; forest inventories; pattern; ecology; global change pattern; ecology; processes; forest inventories; global change	terrestrial plant community dynamics (38.18, 1.0E-4); forest inventories (18.96, 1.0E-4); ecology (18.96, 1.0E-4); processes (18.96, 1.0E-4); study (18.96, 1.0E-4)	covid-19 pandemic (0.02); waste management (0); fu
30	7	0.995	2013	oceanographic and marine cross-domain data management for sustainable development foreword	sustainable development foreword (22.47, 1.0E-4); marine cross-domain data management (22.47, 1.0E-4); covid-19 pandemic (0.06, 1.0); essential variable (0.02, 1.0); critical review (0.01, 1.0)	covid-19 pandemic (0.02); waste management (0.01);
35	5	0.999	2013	long-term environmental research; upper washita river; nutrient transport pattern upper washita river; long-term environmental research; nutrient transport pattern	nutrient transport pattern (42.17, 1.0E-4); long-term environmental research (20.74, 1.0E-4); upper washita river (20.74, 1.0E-4); covid-19 pandemic (0.13, 1.0); waste management (0.04, 1.0)	covid-19 pandemic (0.02); waste management (0); fu
47	3	1	2020	ocean-atmosphere carbon; tropospheric ozone trend; modeling system; stratospheric composition; nasa geos composition forecast covid-19 lockdown measure; modeling system; stratospheric composition; nasa geos composition forecast; covid-19 vaccine	using high spatial resolution observation (93.54, 1.0E-4); covid-19 economic downturn (62.19, 1.0E-4); quantifying regional anomalies (62.19, 1.0E-4); western north america (62.19, 1.0E-4); tropospheric ozone trend (62.19, 1.0E-4)	covid-19 pandemic (0.01); waste management (0); fu

Appendix 2. Publications in the selected clusters of the literature about research infrastructure.

Cluster 3

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
15	2	0	Zilioli, M (2021-JAN) Enabling the reuse of long-term marine biological observations in essential variables frameworks through a practical approach . FRONTIERS IN MARINE SCIENCE DOI 10.3389/fmars.2021.645997
12	120	0	Eisenhauer, N (2019-JAN) A multitrophic perspective on biodiversity-ecosystem functioning research . MECHANISMS UNDERLYING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM FUNCTION, V61, P54 DOI 10.1016/bs.aecr.2019.06.001
11	15	0	Musche, M (2019-JAN) Research questions to facilitate the future development of european long-term ecosystem research infrastructures: a horizon scanning exercise . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V250, P17 DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109479
10	59	0	Trogisch, S (2021-JAN) The significance of tree-tree interactions for forest ecosystem functioning . BASIC AND APPLIED ECOLOGY, V55, P20 DOI 10.1016/j.baee.2021.02.003
9	106	0	Grossman, JJ (2018-JAN) Synthesis and future research directions linking tree diversity to growth, survival, and damage in a global network of tree diversity experiments . ENVIRONMENTAL AND EXPERIMENTAL BOTANY, V152, P22 DOI 10.1016/j.envexpbot.2017.12.015
9	27	0	Jing, X (2021-JAN) Above- and below-ground complementarity rather than selection drive tree diversity-productivity relationships in european forests . FUNCTIONAL ECOLOGY, V35, P12 DOI 10.1111/1365-2435.13825
9	14	0	Zilioli, M (2019-JAN) Feeding essential biodiversity variables (ebvs): actual and potential contributions from lter-italy . NATURE CONSERVATION-BULGARIA DOI 10.3897/natureconservation.34.30735
8	167	0	Novick, KA (2018-JAN) The ameriflux network: a coalition of the willing . AGRICULTURAL AND FOREST METEOROLOGY, V249, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.agrformet.2017.10.009
8	210	0	Farley, SS (2018-JAN) Situating ecology as a big-data science: current advances, challenges, and solutions . BIOSCIENCE, V68, P14 DOI 10.1093/biosci/biy068
8	17	0	Morin, X (2020-JAN) Using forest gap models and experimental data to explore long-term effects of tree diversity on the productivity of mixed planted forests . ANNALS OF FOREST SCIENCE, V77, P19 DOI 10.1007/s13595-020-00954-0
8	33	0	Williams, LJ (2021-JAN) Enhanced light interception and light use efficiency explain overyielding in young tree communities . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V24, P11 DOI 10.1111/ele.13717
7	192	0	Mirtl, M (2018-JAN) Genesis, goals and achievements of long-term ecological research at the global scale: a critical review of lter and future directions . SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V626, P24 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.001
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5	71	0	Watt, E (2021-JAN) Ocean plastics: environmental implications and potential routes for mitigation - a perspective. RSC ADVANCES, V11, P16 DOI 10.1039/d1ra00353d
5	5	0	Karpova, E (2022-JAN) Features of the accumulation of macroplastic on the river bottom in the mekong delta and the impact on fish and decapods. ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION DOI 10.1016/j.envpol.2021.118747
4	15	0	Palmas, F (2022-JAN) Rivers of waste: anthropogenic litter in intermittent sardinian rivers, italy. ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION, V302, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119073
4	29	0	Sun, X (2022-JAN) Biobased plastic: a plausible solution toward carbon neutrality in plastic industry?. JOURNAL OF HAZARDOUS MATERIALS DOI 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129037
4	4	0	Chmielewski, J (2022-JAN) Microplastic in the environment. the role of education in raising social awareness of the handling of plastic waste. JOURNAL OF ELEMENTOLOGY, V27, P15 DOI 10.5601/jelem.2021.26.4.2215
4	32	0	Abhilash (2022-JAN) Recycling of plastic wastes generated from covid-19: a comprehensive illustration of type and properties of plastics with remedial options. SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V838, P20 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155895
4	68	0	Deng, J (2022-JAN) Microplastics released from food containers can suppress lysosomal activity in mouse macrophages. JOURNAL OF HAZARDOUS MATERIALS, V435, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128980
4	194	0	Jiang, J (2022-JAN) From plastic waste to wealth using chemical recycling: a review. JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL CHEMICAL ENGINEERING, V10, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.jece.2021.106867
4	11	0	Johnson, H (2022-JAN) Conceptualizing the transnational regulation of plastics: moving towards a preventative and just agenda for plastics. TRANSNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW, V11, P31 DOI 10.1017/S2047102521000261
4	23	0	Hira, A (2022-JAN) Plastic waste mitigation strategies: a review of lessons from developing countries. JOURNAL OF DEVELOPING SOCIETIES, V38, P24 DOI 10.1177/0169796X221104855
3	42	0	Vriend, P (2021-JAN) Plastic pollution research in indonesia: state of science and future research directions to reduce impacts. FRONTIERS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE DOI 10.3389/fenvs.2021.692907
3	2	0	Sagapova, N (2022-JAN) The academic interest for bioplastics - a bibliometric analysis. EKONOMIA I SRODOWISKO-ECONOMICS AND ENVIRONMENT, V80, P18 DOI 10.34659/eis.2022.80.1.436

3	124	0	Khoo, KS (2021-JAN) Plastic waste associated with the covid-19 pandemic: crisis or opportunity? . JOURNAL OF HAZARDOUS MATERIALS, V417, P16 DOI 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126108
3	26	0	Conchubhair, DO (2019-JAN) Joint effort among research infrastructures to quantify the impact of plastic debris in the ocean . ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH LETTERS DOI 10.1088/1748-9326/ab17ed
3	26	0	Saldana-serrano, M (2022-JAN) Microplastics and linear alkylbenzene levels in oysters crassostrea gigas driven by sewage contamination at an important aquaculture area of brazil . CHEMOSPHERE, V307, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.136039
3	37	0	Lee, WS (2022-JAN) Fluorescent polypropylene nanoplastics for studying uptake, biodistribution, and excretion in zebrafish embryos . ACS OMEGA DOI 10.1021/acsomega.1c06779
3	26	0	Wang, Q (2022-JAN) The covid-19 pandemic reshapes the plastic pollution research - a comparative analysis of plastic pollution research before and during the pandemic . ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH, V208, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.envres.2021.112634

Cluster 20

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
8	23	0	Angelstam, P (2021-JAN) Frontiers of protected areas versus forest exploitation: assessing habitat network functionality in 16 case study regions globally . AMBIO, V50, P25 DOI 10.1007/s13280-021-01628-5
7	64	0	Angelstam, P (2020-JAN) Sweden does not meet agreed national and international forest biodiversity targets: a call for adaptive landscape planning . LANDSCAPE AND URBAN PLANNING, V202, P17 DOI 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2020.103838
7	17	0	Angelstam, P (2021-JAN) Effects of forestry intensification and conservation on green infrastructures: a spatio-temporal evaluation in sweden . LAND, V10, P29 DOI 10.3390/land10050531
6	28	0	Angelstam, P (2021-JAN) Maintaining natural and traditional cultural green infrastructures across europe: learning from historic and current landscape transformations . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V36, P27 DOI 10.1007/s10980-020-01161-y
6	23	0	Angelstam, P (2021-JAN) Meeting places and social capital supporting rural landscape stewardship: a pan-european horizon scanning . ECOLOGY AND SOCIETY, V26, P86 DOI 10.5751/ES-12110-260111
5	19	0	Manton, M (2021-JAN) Assessment and spatial planning for peatland conservation and restoration: europe's trans-border neman river basin as a case study . LAND, V10, P27 DOI 10.3390/land10020174
4	76	0	Kuuluvainen, T (2021-JAN) Natural disturbance-based forest management: moving beyond retention and continuous-cover forestry . FRONTIERS IN FORESTS AND GLOBAL CHANGE DOI 10.3389/ffgc.2021.629020
4	10	0	Angelstam, P (2020-JAN) Landscape approach towards integrated conservation and use of primeval forests: the transboundary kovda river catchment in russia and finland . LAND DOI 10.3390/land9050144
3	21	0	Pedroza-arceo, NM (2022-JAN) A knowledge review on integrated landscape approaches . FORESTS, V13, P24 DOI 10.3390/f13020312
3	76	0	Plieninger, T (2020-JAN) Agroforestry for sustainable landscape management . SUSTAINABILITY SCIENCE, V15, P12 DOI 10.1007/s11625-020-00836-4
3	14	0	Stryamets, N (2020-JAN) Governance of non-wood forest products in russia and ukraine: institutional rules, stakeholder arrangements, and decision-making processes . LAND USE POLICY, V94, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104289
3	5	0	Nishi, M (2022-JAN) Health and landscape approaches: a comparative review of integrated approaches to health and landscape management . ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & POLICY, V136, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.envsci.2022.06.015
2	5	0	Axelsson, R (2020-JAN) The challenge of transdisciplinary research: a case study of learning by evaluation for sustainable transport infrastructures . SUSTAINABILITY, V12, P24 DOI 10.3390/su12176995
2	1	0	Mehnen, N (2023-JAN) Periphery and integrated planning: coping with rural and touristic challenges across scales in the german wadden sea region . LAND, V12, P21 DOI 10.3390/land12040904
2	2	0	Riggs, RA (2021-JAN) Common ground: integrated landscape approaches and small and medium forest enterprises for vibrant forest landscapes . SUSTAINABILITY SCIENCE, V16, P14 DOI 10.1007/s11625-021-01035-5
2	55	0	Koivula, M (2020-JAN) Experimental evidence on biodiversity impacts of variable retention forestry, prescribed burning, and deadwood manipulation in fennoscandia . ECOLOGICAL PROCESSES DOI 10.1186/s13717-019-0209-1
2	52	0	Turner, BL (2020-JAN) Framing the search for a theory of land use . JOURNAL OF LAND USE SCIENCE, V15, P20 DOI 10.1080/1747423X.2020.1811792
2	18	0	Njoroge, P (2020-JAN) Steering energy transitions through landscape governance: case of mathare informal settlement, nairobi, kenya . LAND DOI 10.3390/land9060206

2	5	0	Hemmati, M (2021-JAN) Perceiver, perceived and perceptual product (evaluating experts' interpretations of the components of 'landscape' definition) . MANZAR-THE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF LANDSCAPE, V13, P16 DOI 10.22034/MANZAR.2021.273356.2115
2	8	0	Kienast, F (2021-JAN) Landscape ecology reaching out . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V36, P10 DOI 10.1007/s10980-021-01301-y
2	13	0	Darvishi, A (2022-JAN) Assessing levels, trade-offs and synergies of landscape services in the iranian province of qazvin: towards sustainable landscapes . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V37, P23 DOI 10.1007/s10980-021-01337-0
2	6	0	Mekki, I (2022-JAN) Oasis extension trajectories in kebili territory, southern tunisia: drivers of development and actors' discourse . NEW MEDIT, V21, P17 DOI 10.30682/nm2205f
2	167	0	Wu, J (2021-JAN) Landscape sustainability science (ii): core questions and key approaches . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V36, P33 DOI 10.1007/s10980-021-01245-3
2	7	0	Laroche, G (2020-JAN) Exploring the social coherence of rural landscapes featuring agroforestry intercropping systems using locals' visual assessments and perceptions . SUSTAINABILITY SCIENCE, V15, P19 DOI 10.1007/s11625-020-00837-3
2	7	0	Dawson, L (2021-JAN) Bogs, birds, and berries in belarus: the governance and management dynamics of wetland restoration in a state-centric, top-down context . ECOLOGY AND SOCIETY, V26, P60 DOI 10.5751/ES-12139-260108
2	16	0	Angelstam, P (2022-JAN) Tradition as asset or burden for transitions from forests as cropping systems to multifunctional forest landscapes: sweden as a case study . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V505, P17 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119895
2	4	0	Girao, I (2023-JAN) Trends in high nature value farmland and ecosystem services valuation: a bibliometric review . LAND, V12, P28 DOI 10.3390/land12101952
2	30	0	Martinez, pastur GJ (2020-JAN) Ecological perspectives on variable retention forestry . ECOLOGICAL PROCESSES DOI 10.1186/s13717-020-0215-3
2	29	0	Qiu, J (2021-JAN) Land-use intensity mediates ecosystem service tradeoffs across regional social-ecological systems . ECOSYSTEMS AND PEOPLE, V17, P15 DOI 10.1080/26395916.2021.1925743
2	6	0	Angelstam, P (2022-JAN) Barriers and bridges for sustaining functional habitat networks: a macroecological system analysis of wet grassland landscapes . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P20 DOI 10.1002/ece3.8801
2	0	0	Rose, RAC (2020-JAN) Landscape planning and management at klebang, melaka . GEOGRAFIA-MALAYSIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIETY & SPACE, V16, P15 DOI 10.17576/geo-2020-1602-08

Appendix 3. Clusters summary for the literature about research and/or monitoring programs.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	197	0.94	2016	future consideration; seasonal change; threatened native fishes; wilderness restoration; mountain lake future consideration; seasonal change; detection tool; temporal scale; freshwater pond	environmental dna (1996.11, 1.0E-4); using environmental dna (869.92, 1.0E-4); freshwater pond (352.31, 1.0E-4); citizen science (339.14, 1.0E-4); invasive fish species (326.01, 1.0E-4)	endangered stream frog (2.55); remnant amphibian p
2	100	0.959	2018	ecological fieldwork; regional analysis; distribution pattern; benthic assemblage; information cost acoustic monitoring; changing ecosystem; long-term ichthyoplankton monitoring dataset; spawning phenology; dpcr method	management strategies (338.36, 1.0E-4); hydrologic extreme (335.68, 1.0E-4); recreational fishery (308.94, 1.0E-4); citizen science (275.85, 1.0E-4); species richness (234.15, 1.0E-4)	invasive mosquito species (2.17); identifying ecol
4	78	0.991	2010	natural resource; citizen-driven intertidal monitoring program; survey design; socioecological praxis; managing decline environmental monitoring; rocky intertidal communities; northeast spain; comparing monitoring data; managing decline	citizen science (753.1, 1.0E-4); environmental dna (255.22, 1.0E-4); integrating studies (228.4, 1.0E-4); natural system (228.4, 1.0E-4); global citizen science dataset (223.42, 1.0E-4)	landscape composition (0.58); endangered stream fr
5	68	0.913	2018	catching invasive; essential component; different distributional range; qualitative synthesis; brazilian coast potential participant; passive edna; environmental sustainability; effective monitoring; fishy business-assessing	environmental dna (399.21, 1.0E-4); community-based monitoring (296.72, 1.0E-4); citizen science (224.52, 1.0E-4); citizen science application (219.27, 1.0E-4); lake water quality (215.2, 1.0E-4)	whole community inventories (0.98); landscape comp
9	58	1	2008	enriching effluent; food web; preterm labor; san francisco bay; marine environment enriching effluent; chilean river; filamentous cyanobacterium trichormus; future research; vitro modulation	environmental effect (234.88, 1.0E-4); marine environment (184.86, 1.0E-4); food web (177.72, 1.0E-4); san francisco bay (177.72, 1.0E-4); reducing methylmercury accumulation (177.72, 1.0E-4)	sources fate (0.17); emerging organic contaminant
11	40	0.988	2021	marine litter; literature review; plastic waste; clean-up activities; accumulation pattern environmental plastic abundance; antarctic peninsula region; global action; research priorities; plastic debris	plastic debris (174.31, 1.0E-4); worlds ocean (158.4, 1.0E-4); literature review (150.45, 1.0E-4); marine litter (150.45, 1.0E-4); clean-up activities (150.45, 1.0E-4)	marine megafauna (0.11); humboldt current system (
12	37	0.965	2019	national forest inventories; global genetic diversity status; national forest inventory; quality evaluation; using planktom12 practical application; national forest inventories; global genetic diversity status; land cover data set; national forest inventory	lcmmap collection (366.63, 1.0E-4); environmental dna (341.67, 1.0E-4); genetic diversity (335.57, 1.0E-4); national forest inventory (264.67, 1.0E-4); regional land cover land use (229.27, 1.0E-4)	qinghai-tibet plateau (0.8); quality evaluation (0
14	35	0.996	2018	light pollution; bat conservation; dark ecological network; acoustic monitoring; urban area indirect measure; feeding ground; gray whale density; seismic survey; automated identification error	seismic survey (446.55, 1.0E-4); western gray whale (349.96, 1.0E-4); feeding ground (333.91, 1.0E-4); artificial light (182.12, 1.0E-4); foraging season (158.27, 1.0E-4)	landscape composition (0.11); insectivorous bat (0
18	29	0.976	2015	sample fixative; voucher-preserving biodiversity assessment method; high-throughput environmental dna analysis; biological assessment; urban stream urban river; absence data; dna barcode library; routine stream monitoring; aquatic biodiversity survey	metabarcoding-based macroinvertebrate identification (120.98, 1.0E-4); routine stream monitoring (120.98, 1.0E-4); assessing strength (120.98, 1.0E-4); dna metabarcoding (112.33, 1.0E-4); freshwater macroinvertebrate bioassessment (111.55, 1.0E-4)	landscape composition (0.04); endangered stream fr
25	24	0.995	2007	dioxin-furan teq; literature-based confirmation; total pcb; diphenyl ether; histological lesion great lake; temporal trend; erie fish communities; bayesian assessment; top predator fish	critical factor (89.25, 1.0E-4); great lakes region (89.25, 1.0E-4); contaminant biomonitoring program (89.25, 1.0E-4); temporal trend (79.63, 1.0E-4); bayesian assessment (78.03, 1.0E-4)	environmental dna (0.03); national monitoring netw
29	18	0.98	2020	education professor; research program planning; citizen science; systematic review; multi-sited transition program education professor; transdisciplinary research program; interdisciplinary collaboration; transdisciplinary integration; creating favorable condition	transdisciplinary integration (109.63, 1.0E-4); empirical insight (109.63, 1.0E-4); creating favorable condition (109.63, 1.0E-4); interdisciplinary collaboration (98.59, 1.0E-4); agri-food transformation research (98.59, 1.0E-4)	environmental dna (0.03); education professor (0.0

31	17	0.999	1996	statistical issue; natural resource; forest plan; regional monitoring strategy; aquatic ecosystem aquatic ecosystem; sample survey design issue; environmental sampling; regional assessment; elemental fish tissue contamination	critical element (110.09, 1.0E-4); aquatic resource (110.09, 1.0E-4); local diversity (99.01, 1.0E-4); regional pattern (99.01, 1.0E-4); anthropogenic disturbance (99.01, 1.0E-4)	environmental dna (0.03); statistical issue (0.02)
32	17	1	2018	prevalence; australian community; prescribed neuropsychiatric drug; passive sampler; australia wastewater analysis; global trend; new psychoactive substance; wastewater-based epidemiology; artificial sweetener consumption	wastewater-based epidemiology (353.92, 1.0E-4); pain treatment (123.17, 1.0E-4); wastewater analysis (123.17, 1.0E-4); enhanced direct injection (113.65, 1.0E-4); in-sewer stability (113.65, 1.0E-4)	prevalence (0.04); gout (0.04); australia (0.04);
40	13	1	2017	trade measure; unregulated fishing; legal analysis; fishing vessels behavior identification; combating iuu fishing trade measure; harvest location; traceability intervention; unregulated fishing; thornback ray	traceability intervention (97.92, 1.0E-4); trader responses (97.92, 1.0E-4); elemental fingerprinting (86.98, 1.0E-4); muscle tissue (86.98, 1.0E-4); food safety assessment (86.98, 1.0E-4)	environmental dna (0.03); legal analysis (0.02); u

Appendix 4. Publications in the selected clusters of the literature about research and monitoring programs.

Cluster 0

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
45	744	0	Barnes, MA (2016-JAN) The ecology of environmental dna and implications for conservation genetics . CONSERVATION GENETICS, V17, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10592-015-0775-4
44	64	0	Coble, AA (2019-JAN) Edna as a tool for identifying freshwater species in sustainable forestry: a critical review and potential future applications . SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V649, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.370
43	400	0	Beng, KC (2020-JAN) Applications of environmental dna (edna) in ecology and conservation: opportunities, challenges and prospects . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P33 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-01980-0
40	88	0	Evans, NT (2018-JAN) Freshwater fisheries assessment using environmental dna: a primer on the method, its potential, and shortcomings as a conservation tool . FISHERIES RESEARCH DOI 10.1016/j.fishres.2017.09.013
40	80	0	Freeland, JR (2017-JAN) The importance of molecular markers and primer design when characterizing biodiversity from environmental dna . GENOME, V60, P17 DOI 10.1139/gen-2016-0100
38	167	0	Harper, LR (2019-JAN) Prospects and challenges of environmental dna (edna) monitoring in freshwater ponds . HYDROBIOLOGIA, V826, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10750-018-3750-5
36	721	0	Goldberg, CS (2016-JAN) Critical considerations for the application of environmental dna methods to detect aquatic species . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12595
33	164	0	Hansen, BK (2018-JAN) The sceptical optimist: challenges and perspectives for the application of environmental dna in marine fisheries . FISH AND FISHERIES, V19, P18 DOI 10.1111/faf.12286
33	55	0	Adams, CIM (2019-JAN) A brief review of non-avian reptile environmental dna (edna), with a case study of painted turtle (chrysemys picta) edna under field conditions . DIVERSITY-BASEL, V11, P22 DOI 10.3390/d11040050
33	139	0	Stewart, KA (2019-JAN) Understanding the effects of biotic and abiotic factors on sources of aquatic environmental dna . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V28, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-019-01709-8
33	193	0	Tillotson, MD (2018-JAN) Concentrations of environmental dna (edna) reflect spawning salmon abundance at fine spatial and temporal scales . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V220, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2018.01.030
32	50	0	Mauvisseau, Q (2018-JAN) Environmental dna as an efficient tool for detecting invasive crayfishes in freshwater ponds . HYDROBIOLOGIA, V805, P13 DOI 10.1007/s10750-017-3288-y
31	55	0	Adrian-kalchhauser, I (2016-JAN) An edna assay to monitor a globally invasive fish species from flowing freshwater . PLOS ONE, V11, P22 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0147558
30	85	0	Balasingham, KD (2018-JAN) Environmental dna detection of rare and invasive fish species in two great lakes tributaries . MOLECULAR ECOLOGY, V27, P16 DOI 10.1111/mec.14395
30	12	0	Ostberg, CO (2018-JAN) Distribution and seasonal differences in pacific lamprey and lampetra spp edna across 18 puget sound watersheds . PEERJ DOI 10.7717/peerj.4496
30	134	0	Lear, G (2018-JAN) Methods for the extraction, storage, amplification and sequencing of dna from environmental samples . NEW ZEALAND JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V42, P51 DOI 10.20417/nzjecol.42.9
30	83	0	Machler, E (2016-JAN) Fishing in the water: effect of sampled water volume on environmental dna-based detection of macroinvertebrates . ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY DOI 10.1021/acs.est.5b04188
29	168	0	Eichmiller, JJ (2016-JAN) Optimizing techniques to capture and extract environmental dna for detection and quantification of fish . MOLECULAR ECOLOGY RESOURCES, V16, P13 DOI 10.1111/1755-0998.12421
28	21	0	Davison, PI (2016-JAN) Laboratory and field validation of a simple method for detecting four species of non-native freshwater fish using edna . JOURNAL OF FISH BIOLOGY, V89, P12 DOI 10.1111/jfb.13086
27	47	0	Chambert, T (2018-JAN) An analytical framework for estimating aquatic species density from environmental dna . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.3764
26	291	0	Wilcox, TM (2016-JAN) Understanding environmental dna detection probabilities: a case study using a stream-dwelling char salvelinus fontinalis . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2015.12.023

26	38	0	Gingera, TD (2016-JAN) Detection and identification of lampreys in great lakes streams using environmental dna . JOURNAL OF GREAT LAKES RESEARCH, V42, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.jglr.2016.02.017
26	224	0	Eichmiller, JJ (2016-JAN) Effects of temperature and trophic state on degradation of environmental dna in lake water . ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY DOI 10.1021/acs.est.5b05672
26	319	0	Port, JA (2016-JAN) Assessing vertebrate biodiversity in a kelp forest ecosystem using environmental dna . MOLECULAR ECOLOGY, V25, P15 DOI 10.1111/mec.13481
25	40	0	Currier, CA (2018-JAN) Validation of environmental dna (edna) as a detection tool for at-risk freshwater pearly mussel species (bivalvia: unionidae) . AQUATIC CONSERVATION-MARINE AND FRESHWATER ECOSYSTEMS, V28, P14 DOI 10.1002/aqc.2869
24	76	0	Mauvisseau, Q (2019-JAN) Influence of accuracy, repeatability and detection probability in the reliability of species-specific edna based approaches . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS DOI 10.1038/s41598-018-37001-y
24	177	0	Goldberg, CS (2015-JAN) Moving environmental dna methods from concept to practice for monitoring aquatic macroorganisms . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.040
23	196	0	Yamamoto, S (2016-JAN) Environmental dna as a 'snapshot' of fish distribution: a case study of japanese jack mackerel in maizuru bay, sea of japan . PLOS ONE, V11, P18 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0149786
23	33	0	Akre, TS (2019-JAN) Concurrent visual encounter sampling validates edna selectivity and sensitivity for the endangered wood turtle (glyptemys insculpta) . PLOS ONE, V14, P22 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0215586
22	25	0	Takahashi, S (2020-JAN) Comparing the efficiency of open and enclosed filtration systems in environmental dna quantification for fish and jellyfish . PLOS ONE, V15, P23 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0231718
22	352	0	Turner, CR (2015-JAN) Fish environmental dna is more concentrated in aquatic sediments than surface water . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V183, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.017
22	36	0	Eble, JA (2020-JAN) Marine environmental dna: approaches, applications, and opportunities . ADVANCES IN MARINE BIOLOGY, VOL 86, V86, P29 DOI 10.1016/bs.amb.2020.01.001
22	39	0	Cowart, DA (2018-JAN) Environmental dna (edna) applications for the conservation of imperiled crayfish (decapoda: astacidea) through monitoring of invasive species barriers and relocated populations . JOURNAL OF CRUSTACEAN BIOLOGY, V38, P10 DOI 10.1093/jcbiol/ruy007
21	52	0	Yates, MC (2021-JAN) Integrating physiology and environmental dynamics to operationalize environmental dna (edna) as a means to monitor freshwater macro-organism abundance . MOLECULAR ECOLOGY, V30, P20 DOI 10.1111/mec.16202
21	13	0	Kamoroff, C (2018-JAN) Environmental dna quantification in a spatial and temporal context: a case study examining the removal of brook trout from a high alpine basin . LIMNOLOGY DOI 10.1007/s10201-018-0551-5
21	20	0	Robinson, CV (2019-JAN) Effect of artificial barriers on the distribution of the invasive signal crayfish and chinese mitten crab . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS DOI 10.1038/s41598-019-43570-3
21	49	0	Robinson, CV (2018-JAN) Simultaneous detection of invasive signal crayfish, endangered white-clawed crayfish and the crayfish plague pathogen using environmental dna . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V222, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2018.04.009
21	40	0	Harper, KJ (2018-JAN) Searching for a signal: environmental dna (edna) for the detection of invasive signal crayfish, pacifastacus leniusculus (dana, 1852) . MANAGEMENT OF BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS DOI 10.3391/mbi.2018.9.2.07
20	41	0	Kamoroff, C (2018-JAN) An issue of life or death: using edna to detect viable individuals in wilderness restoration . FRESHWATER SCIENCE, V37, P12 DOI 10.1086/699203
20	41	0	Shaw, JLA (2017-JAN) Using environmental (e)dna sequencing for aquatic biodiversity surveys: a beginner's guide . MARINE AND FRESHWATER RESEARCH, V68, P14 DOI 10.1071/MF15361
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Appendix 5. Organized selected literature

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